

Editorial

The Geography of Gender: Place, Space and Contexts

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Guest Editor, *postScriptum* Special Issue on 'The Geography of Gender: Place, Space and Contexts'

... continued after the Editorial (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7559003) of Volume VII Number ii (July 2022), the first part of the special issues of this journal on 'The Geography of Gender: Place, Space and Contexts' ...

It is always a matter of joy and pride to bring out a sequel to a special issue of a journal. The previous issue (July 2022) of *postScriptum* focused on the intersection of space, place, and gender issues. The theme 'The Geography of Gender: Place, Space, and Contexts' initially sounded a bit uncommon and we were apprehensive of a low number of submissions. But to our utter surprise, the response was huge, and the papers that we received were varied, rich, and inclusive. The total number of submissions was more than forty, and out of them, we selected twenty-one papers (nineteen articles and two book reviews). The July 2022 issue brought out eleven articles and one book review. The present issue (January 2023) offers eight articles and one book review. This huge response not only points to the richness of the topic but also signals a growing interest among researchers in *postScriptum*. I feel content and happy to be a part of this enterprise. I also take the opportunity to thank all the contributors for showing their interest and bestowing their faith on us.

The present issue of *postScriptum* has eight articles that intend to explore various aspects of the intersections of space, place, and gender issues in various contexts. The first article is a special article where Dr Arnab Sinha explores the complex notion of *Azaadi* in the context of Kashmir and also aims to analyze the notion of freedom from the

perspective of the suffering of women. Dr Ellen Dengel-Janic's article urges Anna Burns *Milkman* to study the cultural and political significance of walking and to re-think walking as a democratic practice in the trying times. Dwitiya Sarkar's article deals with Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Cell One* to analyze how different spaces play a serious role in structuring gender identity. Nasrin Shahnaz and Dr Merry Baruah Bora, in their article, read Arundhati Roy's *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness* in the light of Foucault's Heterotopia and Edward Soja's *The Third Space*. Ritu Madan's article studies Jyotirmoyee Devi's 'Shei Chheleta' to map post-partition Delhi and uncover the covered or lost stories of the abducted women that were ignored or hidden behind the dominant narratives of the official history. VR Arundev's article engages in studying the interrelationship between hyper-masculinity and urbanity in the much acclaimed Malayalam gangster thriller *Malik*. The article tried to analyze the link between the development of hypermasculine traits in men and the socio-political conditions of the urban space where they are posited. Dr. Ricardo J. Millhouse's article explores the relationship between gender, race, memory, and spectral geographies in Mobile, Alabama, and also tries to locate the impact of this relationship on the fields of gender studies, black studies, and geography. Abhigyan Guha's article aims at advancing feminist foreign policy-making in international relations. Ms. Arpita Dutta has reviewed Bhaswati Ghosh's novel *Victory Colony 1950* and focuses on the transformed role of the refugee women and their relationship with the migrated place. Like the previous issue, the present issue also successfully established the multilayered and variegated aspects of the focal theme.

As the guest editor of this special issue, I would like to extend my heartfelt thanks to the entire team of *postScriptum* and the contributors who brought this project to fruition. As of now, over to the readers.